

Performance Evaluation of a Light-Tree Point-to-Multipoint Metro-Core Architecture in Correlated Traffic Scenarios

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Abstract—We investigate the performance of a light-tree based point-to-multipoint (P2MP) architecture that places P2MP hub transceivers in the metro-core network, under correlated traffic conditions. The evaluation was performed using a novel algorithm that leverages the traffic correlations among the P2MP spokes/access aggregators to optimize the placement of hub transceivers and minimize the respective costs. Simulation results demonstrate that the algorithm performs effectively in several correlated traffic scenarios and also provides the highest cost benefit for randomly correlated spoke traffic.

Keywords—Coherent transceivers, coherent point-to-multipoint, access optical network, metro optical network, dynamic resource allocation, correlated traffic

I. INTRODUCTION

The metro-access optical continuum is envisaged as a key enabler for the evolution of the corresponding network segments, so as to meet the enhanced capacity and latency requirements of the future [1]. Its implementation will require existing state-of-the-art technologies, such as flexible transceivers and ROADMs, as well as evolutionary architectures that incorporate them in the metro-core network [2]. Within this context, we recently proposed a metro-core P2MP architecture [3], which takes full advantage of the enhanced resource allocation capabilities of coherent digital-subcarrier-multiplexing (DSM) transceivers [4]. The architecture utilizes light-trees to connect spokes/access network aggregators from multiple horseshoes to P2MP roots/hubs that are placed at the metro-core nodes. Ideally, the hubs are placed directly at backbone network nodes, thus reducing the need for point-to-point connections from the metro-core to the backbone. Light-trees also eliminate intermediate O/E/O conversions, providing deterministic latency for crossing these network segments. Simultaneously, they contribute to the consolidation of routers, leading to significant cost and energy savings in both the optical and IP layers [5].

The purpose of this work is to investigate the suitability of the light-tree architecture in scenarios where the spoke traffic is dynamic and also exhibits correlations. For instance, it has been previously argued that the traffic from business users peaks at a different time from residential users [6]. As a result, the spokes that predominantly serve one of the two user types will experience highly-correlated traffic. On the other hand, the correlation between the “business” spokes and “residential” spokes can be positive or negative depending on the hour of the day, following the analysis presented in Ref. [7]. Given the network topology, the correlation properties

may extend to the horseshoes, assuming that they interconnect spokes with similar traffic profiles.

Previous works on the light-tree architecture have mainly focused on fixed traffic scenarios, which do not fully encompass the dynamic nature of access network aggregation. DSM transceivers, on the other hand, can adapt to the network dynamics and correlations since it is possible to re-allocate the digital subcarriers (DSCs) of the hub to the connected spokes dynamically, based on their requests. It was previously shown that this approach can impart significant cost savings in a P2MP scenario provided that the spokes are clustered in a fashion that ensures that their sum rate (in DSCs) does not exceed the hub capacity [7]. This effect can also be exploited and possibly magnified in the light-tree P2MP architecture, which allows for the multiplexing of spokes from multiple horseshoes. It is then less challenging to find a suitable combination of spokes that leverages their traffic correlations and ensures that the available hub resources are not exceeded.

In the current work, we propose a heuristic resource allocation algorithm that efficiently associates spokes with hubs and ensures that the hub capacity is only exceeded with a targeted service level (low or zero probability of additional capacity blocking). The validity of the algorithm is verified via simulations and it is demonstrated that it efficiently allocates the hub resources in all the considered traffic scenarios, which include independent, positively correlated and randomly correlated traffic. Compared to other algorithms, for example Integer Linear Programming (ILP), the heuristic approach has been previously shown to provide similar close-to-optimal solutions at significantly reduced execution times for the network size and parameter space under consideration [8], which is also true in this work. Finally, the proposed algorithm outperforms heuristics that efficiently solve similar problems with probabilistic constraints [9], and finds solutions that require a smaller number of P2MP hub transceivers.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION ALGORITHM

The light-tree P2MP architecture, which is depicted in Fig. 1, connects access aggregators that are located at the horseshoes with metro or backbone nodes. This is accomplished by equipping the access aggregators with P2MP spoke transceivers that employ DSM, and communicate with hub/root transceivers of similar technology. Additionally, the architecture requires broadcast-and-select or broadcast-capable switch-and-select ROADMs in the metro-core network segment [3]. These ROADMs extend their optical node degree to the fibers

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Fig. 1. Light-tree based P2MP architecture. The orange, green and purple colors denote the allocation of spokes (aggregation nodes) to hubs (metro-core nodes).

of the horseshoe or ring-based metro aggregation network segment, enabling optically transparent light-trees from hubs to spokes.

For the rest of the paper, we will assume that the traffic of each spoke s is a random variable (RV) that is distributed following the truncated Gaussian distribution with parameters $\{T_{min}^s, T_{ave}^s, T_{max}^s, \sigma_T\}$, which correspond to the minimum, most probable, maximum traffic value and the traffic variance, respectively (in Gb/s). The spoke traffic is transported over discrete DSCs, which may employ one of the $\{16\text{-QAM}, 8\text{-QAM}, \text{QPSK}, \text{BPSK}\}$ modulation formats, depending on the physical layer impairment levels. Note that the modeling is generic, and this set and all related assumptions can be extended according to the transceivers' capabilities. The reference modulation format is 16-QAM, where DSCs carry 25 Gb/s each, while the rate of the other formats is reduced by a factor $a_M = \log 16 / \log M$, where M is the modulation order. As a result, the parameters of the spoke traffic can be also represented in a unified manner following $a_M \cdot \{SC_{min}^s, SC_{ave}^s, SC_{max}^s, \sigma\}$, where DSCs are used instead of Gb/s. We assume that the RVs that represent the spoke traffic are correlated with a correlation parameter ρ . The convolution method works for independent traffic, so, since we assume correlation, it is not possible to utilize it to calculate the distributions of their sum traffic. Instead, the multivariate marginal density distributions are required [10], whose calculation involves extensive numerical integrations due to the large number of spokes that are present in the network. To overcome this issue, we assume that each spoke s is associated with a traffic record that contains a series of previous traffic samples $\mathbf{SC}_s = \{SC_{s,1}, SC_{s,2}, \dots, SC_{s,N}\}$. In a real network, the traffic record can be obtained by keeping track of the previous SC requests/assignments and also periodically monitoring the spoke's traffic. The number of samples N should be sufficient to convey the traffic distribution properties but can be also chosen to erase outdated and irrelevant measurements. In a practical application, it will depend on the time-granularity of the traffic changes and on how often the DSCs must be changed or reallocated. If a set of spokes are connected to a hub $h = \{s_1, \dots, s_m\}$, then the corresponding traffic record for the hub is given by the sum of the individual samples of the

Fig. 2. Visualization of the traffic record of $N=100$ samples, for two negatively correlated spokes that are allocated to the same hub. The targeted service level is $P_b = 0$ (assured service).

spokes following $\mathbf{SC}_h = \sum_{s \in h} \mathbf{SC}_s$. Fig. 2 presents a visualization of the traffic records of two negatively correlated spokes that are allocated to the same hub.

Our goal is to allocate spokes to hubs ensuring that both service level and physical layer constraints are met. Regarding the service level, we use the DSC blocking probability of each spoke to allocate a P2MP transceiver to it, and the DSC blocking probabilities of all spokes in a hub to cluster them within the hub and allocate a suitable root P2MP transceiver. Following the previous discussion on the spoke traffic, it is straightforward to calculate the probability that its transceiver capacity is exceeded using the spoke traffic record as $P_{b,s} = 1/N \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N 1_{SC_{s,n} > C_s}$, where C_s is the spoke transceiver capacity in DSCs. Similarly, we evaluate the same probability for hubs as $P_{b,h} = 1/N \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N 1_{SC_{h,n} > C_h}$, where C_h is the hub transceiver capacity. We target a specific service level, expressed by blocking probability P_b for both types, thus we require $P_{b,s} \leq P_b$ and $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$ for all the spokes and all the hubs that will be placed in the network, respectively.

Physical layer constraints are imposed by the available OSNR at the horseshoes and the OSNR degradation that is introduced by the propagation in the metro-core network, following $OSNR^{-1} = OSNR_h^{-1} + OSNR_m^{-1}$. For the metro-core physical layer impairments, we approximated the corresponding OSNR as $OSNR_m(\text{dB}) = 26.0 - 10 \log_{10}(2N_s)$, where N_s is the number of equivalent 80 km links that are traversed by the light-trees and a factor of 2 is included to include the impact of ROADMs. The OSNRs at the horseshoe outputs were set equal to the 16-QAM OSNR threshold (equal to 15.1 dB) plus an additional budget, so it is given by: $OSNR_h(\text{dB}) = 15.1 + \text{budget}$. The available OSNR budget is determined by the access network architecture, including the number of amplifiers and splits that are present in the horseshoes [11], [12]. An allocation of the spoke to a hub is only accepted if the available OSNR exceeds the one that is required by the utilized modulation format $OSNR \geq OSNR_M$, where the OSNR thresholds for the four modulation formats are $OSNR_M = \{15.1, 12.5, 8.5, 5.5\}$ dB [13]. If possible, the spoke can also lower its modulation order

to further utilize the available budget and reach more hubs. However this option requires using a higher number of DSCs and therefore more hubs, given that the service level constraint also exists.

An efficient resource allocation algorithm leverages the traffic correlations between spokes while assigning them to hubs. The goal is to place negatively correlated spokes at the same hub, since their combined traffic has a lower variance than the sum of the individual variances. As a result, it becomes less probable that the combined traffic from the negatively correlated spokes exceeds the available hub capacity, and the service level is achieved more easily. In contrast, the selection of independent or positively correlated spokes increases the traffic variance and negatively affects the capability of the hub to achieve the desired service level.

Our proposed allocation algorithm aims to meet the service and physical layer limitations, and at the same time minimize the number of hub transceivers that are required by exploiting the traffic correlations. To achieve this, the algorithm sorts the spoke requests in descending order based on SC_{ave}^s . The algorithm then iterates over all modulation formats, starting from the highest (16-QAM in the studied scenarios), and during each iteration it examines the sorted spokes that have not been previously allocated to hubs. Given the current modulation order, the algorithm produces for a spoke s at hand a set H^s that contains the metro and backbone nodes that can be reached by that spoke. Then, it generates the traffic samples $SC_h, h \in H^s$ for all the reachable hubs h , and the associated probabilities $P_{b,h}, h \in H^s$. Only hubs that achieve the service level ($P_{b,h} \leq P_b$) are considered further, and if multiple hubs exist then the algorithm selects the one with the maximum $P_{b,h}$. Following this selection, the traffic samples of the hub are updated using $SC_h \leftarrow SC_h + SC_s$, along with the possible hub locations in the metro-core mesh $H^h \leftarrow H^h \cap H^s$. However, if none of the hubs can achieve the desired service level then the spoke (a) connect to a new hub using its current modulation format, or (b) can be examined in a following iteration using a lower modulation format. Option (a) is selected when the spoke is able to reach a backbone node, so as to avoid additional P2P connections between the hub and the backbone. In this case, the new hub is initialized using $SC_h \leftarrow SC_s$ and $H^h \leftarrow H^s$. Option (b) is selected when the spoke can not reach a backbone node, expecting that it will be able to reach one after lowering its modulation order. The pseudocode of the algorithm is presented in Fig. 3.

It should be noted that the presented algorithm does not directly address the correlation properties between spokes, but it considers those indirectly by examining the hubs blocking probabilities. It is expected that the probability $P_{b,h}, h \in H^s$ will be lower for the candidate hubs that are negatively correlated with the spoke under consideration. As a result, these hubs are more likely to be selected for the spoke allocation, and the correlation properties are considered implicitly. This is an important property of the algorithm, enabling it to efficiently solve the allocation problem irrespective of the spoke correlations. The property is further demonstrated in the next section, where several correlation scenarios are examined, including positive and random correlations, as well as independence among the spokes.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm was validated via Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations. To this end, we considered Domain A from the TID

1	Input: Network graph, transceiver sizes and modulation formats, spoke traffic distributions and correlations
2	Output: Placement and configuration of transceivers
3	Constraints: OSNR budget, blocking probability P_b
4	Initialize placement and configuration to an empty set
5	Sort spokes in descending order based on SC_{ave}^s
6	For each modulation format (highest-to-lowest) do :
7	For each unassigned spoke s do :
8	Calculate the traffic samples of the spoke SC_s for the current modulation format
9	Identify the hubs $h \in H^s$ that can be reached using the current modulation format and the available OSNR budget
10	Calculate the traffic samples of the hubs $SC_h + SC_s, h \in H^s$
11	Calculate the blocking probability of the hubs $P_{b,h}, h \in H^s$
12	If one or more hubs satisfy $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$ then :
13	Assign the spoke to the hub with the maximum $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$
14	Update the hub traffic samples $SC_h \leftarrow SC_h + SC_s$
15	Update the hub placement $H^h \leftarrow H^h \cap H^s$
16	Set the modulation format of the spoke to the current one
17	Set the spoke transceiver size equal to the minimum size that satisfies $P_{b,s} \leq P_b$
18	Else If no hubs satisfy $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$ and H^s contains backbone nodes then :
19	Place a new hub and associate it with the spoke
20	Initialize the hub traffic samples $SC_h \leftarrow SC_s$
21	Initialize the hub placement $H^h \leftarrow H^s$
22	Set the modulation format of the spoke to the current one
23	Set the spoke transceiver size equal to the minimum size that satisfies $P_{b,s} \leq P_b$
24	For each hub do :
25	Set the hub transceiver size equal to the minimum size that satisfies $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$
26	If the hub is not located on a backbone node then :
27	Utilize a P2P transceiver having the same size with the hub to reach the backbone

Fig. 3. The pseudocode of the heuristic allocation algorithm.

reference network, which consists of 30 metro-core nodes in total, including 6 backbone nodes [14]. All metro-core nodes connected to a horseshoe with 10 spokes (access aggregators), thus the total number of spokes in the simulation was equal to 300. Each hub and spoke was equipped with a P2MP transceiver whose capacity was equal to $\{32, 16, 8, 4\}$ DSCs and respective costs of $\{3, 2, 1.5, 1\}$ arbitrary units (a.u.). The transceivers were either fixed and supported only 16-QAM, or flexible and supported all available formats $\{16\text{-QAM}, 8\text{-QAM}, \text{QPSK}, \text{BPSK}\}$. The P2P transceivers that connected the intermediate metro-core nodes with the backbone had the same bandwidth, supported 16-QAM only and their cost was reduced by 10% compared to the P2MP transceivers [15].

The MC simulations were performed by generating 1000 traffic instances. In each instance, we first generated the $\{SC_{min}^s, SC_{ave}^s, SC_{max}^s\}$ values for the spokes. The SC_{ave}^s values were uniformly distributed between $\{1, \dots, 20\}$ DSCs, while the corresponding lower and upper minima were set to $\{SC_{min}^s, SC_{max}^s\} = \{0.90, 1.40\} \cdot SC_{ave}^s$. The traffic variance was set equal to $\sigma = 3$. Given these parameters, we then generated $N = 1000$ correlated traffic samples for each spoke using the Gaussian copula method and the inverse cumulative distribution function of the truncated Gaussian distribution [16]. The allocation algorithm was then executed for different values of P_b ($P_b = 0$ and 0.1) and the two types of transceivers (fixed and flexible).

Fig. 4. Total transceiver cost for service level (a) $P_b = 0$ and (b) $P_b = 0.1$. Solid and dashed lines correspond to fixed and flexible transceivers, respectively.

We also studied four different correlation scenarios: the first scenario involved independent traffic samples for the spokes ($\rho = 0$) and is representative of scenarios where each spoke serves all user types. The second scenario involved positively correlated traffic with correlation parameter $\rho = 0.9$, and can be viewed as a worst-case scenario where most of the users belong to the same type and the traffic from the spokes peaks almost simultaneously. The third scenario considered randomly correlated traffic among the spokes, with the same parameter ρ ; here, it is assumed that all user types are present, but each spoke is dominated by a single type of user. Finally, the fourth scenario considered randomly correlated traffic between the horseshoes, corresponding to a scenario where each horseshoe provides access predominantly to a single user type. In this final scenario, all the spokes within the same horseshoe exhibited the same positive correlation, but any given pair of horseshoes was randomly correlated.

The simulation results for the total transceiver cost (including P2MP hubs and spokes, and P2P to connect intermediate hubs to backbone nodes) vs the available OSNR budget (defined in Section II) are presented in Fig. 4. As expected, the positively correlated traffic scenario exhibits the higher transceiver cost, the randomly correlated scenario exhibits the lowest cost, and the randomly correlated horseshoe scenario lies

Fig. 5. Number of hub transceivers for service level (a) $P_b = 0$ and (b) $P_b = 0.1$. Solid and dashed lines correspond to fixed and flexible transceivers, respectively.

between the two. The independent traffic scenario is always the second-most costly. It is also interesting to note that the algorithm maintains the cost reduction properties of the light-tree P2MP architecture as the budget increases, which was first observed for fixed traffic scenarios. Namely, the hubs migrate towards the backbone at higher OSNR budgets, P2P connections are gradually reduced and, after a budget of 2 dB that corresponds to a spoke-to-hub distance of approximately 180 km, they vanish. A full P2MP architecture has been implemented at this point (budget > 2 dB), and the results show that this is always the case irrespective of the traffic scenario.

Furthermore, the number of hubs also decreases with the available OSNR budget contributing to an additional cost reduction. To better illustrate this, we plot the number of hub transceivers that are required by each traffic scenario in Fig. 5. Clearly, a larger number of hubs are required at low OSNR budgets (0 and 0.5 dB). In this case, there is not enough budget for the light-trees to form and the P2MP architecture reverts to the “hub-and-spoke” (H&S) paradigm, where hubs are associated with horseshoes. This is a limitation of the H&S architecture since it is only possible to multiplex traffic from spokes within the same horseshoe. As the OSNR budget increases, more horseshoes become available to hubs and the

proposed algorithm utilizes these additional options to distribute the hub resources to spokes more efficiently. This leads to a significant reduction in the number of hubs that are required and following the results of the figure for fixed transceivers the reduction amounts to 14% - 17% depending on the traffic scenario, with the randomly correlated traffic scenario benefiting the most in both service levels. The implementations with flexible transceivers also require a larger number of hubs due to the utilization of lower capacity modulation formats that expand the number of DSCs that are needed to transport the same traffic. The hub reduction in this case ranges between 19% - 23%. The two implementations converge to the same number of hubs at high OSNR budgets, as expected, since all spokes can use 16-QAM to communicate with the hubs that are placed on the backbone nodes.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The spoke-to-hub allocation problem is a variant of the bin-packing problem with probabilistic constraints, and additional limitations that are imposed by the modulation format selection and hub placement. A related non-probabilistic problem was solved recently in Ref. [8], where it was demonstrated that ILP provides globally optimal solutions, however it is time consuming due to the extensive parameter space (network size, transceiver sizes and modulation formats). It was also argued that a heuristic algorithm, which was based on best-fit decreasing allocation, attains close to optimal solutions at significantly reduced times. A second challenge with using ILP in this problem arises from the fact that the constraints are not linear. Therefore, one needs to revert to best-fit and first-fit heuristics that can find a reasonably close solution to the optimal one for probabilistic constraints [9].

Following the above, it is expected that the proposed algorithm, which implements probabilistic best-fit decreasing with additional physical layer constraints, will also attain close-to-optimal solutions. To verify this, we compared it against the aforementioned best-fit and first-fit algorithms, which both omit the sorting step 3 in the pseudocode of Fig. 3. In addition, the first-fit algorithm also assigns the spoke to the first hub that satisfies $P_{b,h} \leq P_b$ in step 13. The comparison was performed via simulation using the transceiver, network and traffic parameters that have been presented in Section IV. The simulations included the randomly and positively correlated traffic scenarios, which required the minimum and maximum number of hubs, respectively.

The results for the randomly correlated scenario are presented in Fig. 6. The first-fit and best-fit algorithms perform quite close to each other for both probabilities ($P_b = 0$ and $P_b = 0.1$) and transceiver types. It is also evident that the proposed best-fit decreasing heuristic outperforms the other two in all the presented cases, achieving better utilization of the hub capacity and leading to the use of a smaller number of hub transceivers. The hub transceiver reduction ranges between 3% and 7%. The proposed heuristic performs better than first-fit and best-fit in the correlated traffic scenario, as well. The corresponding results are presented in Fig. 7 and a hub transceiver reduction of 2%-6% is observed.

As a closing remark, the execution time of the proposed algorithm is very short, and the results have been obtained using standard computer hardware and Matlab. A single traffic instance can be simulated within approximately 20 seconds, and within this time the algorithm produced results for all 300 spokes, both service levels, both transceiver types, all four

Fig. 6. Comparison between first-fit, best-fit and best-fit decreasing allocation heuristics for randomly correlated spoke traffic. Results for fixed and flexible transceivers are shown in (a) and (b), respectively.

correlation scenarios and all OSNR budgets. Consequently, the algorithm is suitable for fast offline network planning, which has been the target of this work, and can also support the reallocation of spokes to different hubs in real-time operation. It is expected that the reallocation process will be performed infrequently, since several intermediate ROADMs need to be re-configured to establish the new connection, possibly causing service disruption to the spoke users. Given that the algorithm can select a new hub in millisecond timescales, executing steps 6-17 of the pseudocode, the overhead that it introduces seems to be negligible.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented an evaluation of the light-tree based P2MP architecture under correlated traffic scenarios. Using a novel allocation algorithm, we demonstrated that the architecture imparts significant transceiver savings, considering both P2P and P2MP. Simulation results revealed that the P2P transceivers are fully eliminated if an adequately high OSNR budget (2 dB) is available irrespective of the traffic scenario. P2MP hub transceivers are also reduced significantly and, depending on the transceiver technology and traffic correlation scenario, the reduction may range between 14% and 23%. The algorithm

Fig. 7. Comparison between first-fit, best-fit and best-fit decreasing allocation heuristics for positively correlated spoke traffic. Results for fixed and flexible transceivers are shown in (a) and (b), respectively.

provides the best results in scenarios with randomly correlated traffic, where it is easier to identify negatively correlated spokes and assign them to the same hub. The algorithm also provides better solutions compared to heuristics that have been devised to address problems with similar probabilistic constraints.

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